

Analysis of The Influence of Teachers' Teaching Methods and Learning Atmosphere on Students' Understanding Levels at Mi Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is (1) to find out how the teacher's teaching methods influence the level of students' understanding at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang (2) to find out the influence of the learning atmosphere on students' understanding of learning at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang. To obtain the necessary data, the researcher used data collection methods in the form of interviews, observation and documentation, while the analysis method used was a qualitative descriptive method. In this research, the data used were primary and secondary data. The results of this research are (1) the methods used by teachers at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang are effective in increasing students' understanding (2) the learning atmosphere is sufficient to support learning activities coupled with adequate school facilities so as to increase students' understanding of the material. given. Teaching methods and learning atmosphere are two important factors that teachers at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang must pay attention to in order to continue to increase student motivation and interest in learning.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important factor that becomes a milestone for a country and improves the quality of human resources. A country is said to be advanced if education in that country is advanced. In Indonesia itself there is already a law that regulates education, namely Law no . 20 of 2003 mentions the National Education System. According to this law, education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, as well as the skills needed by himself and society.

Education can be implemented through several channels and one of them is formal education held in schools. This educational pathway has clear educational levels, starting from primary education, secondary education, to tertiary education. Apart from that, teachers also have an important role, namely as helpers of students in their physical and spiritual development.

MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang itself is a private school located in Central Java. Even though it is a private school, the school strives to produce quality and high-achieving graduates. This school is faced with challenges in the form of changing times and a continuously changing curriculum. Even so, this school has adapts quite quickly and is able to improve the quality of its students. Apart from providing adequate learning facilities, MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang also pays great attention to the atmosphere of the learning place for its students and teaching methods so that the learning process can run smoothly and increase the learning success of its students.

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in studying more deeply by taking the title "Analysis of the Influence of Teachers' Teaching Methods and Learning Atmosphere on Students' Level of Understanding at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In Indonesia itself there is already a law that regulates education, namely Law no . 20 of 2003 mentions the National Education System. Teaching methods and learning atmosphere are two important factors that teachers at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang must pay attention to in order to continue to increase student motivation and interest in learning.

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

Research Approach

The research approach used by the researcher is a qualitative descriptive research method. This method is used because the data taken by the researcher is in the form of an explanation or presentation and there is no element of calculation in it.

Types of research

The type of research used is descriptive qualitative.

Researcher Presence

The role of the researcher here is as a full observer who has a relationship with the source. The researcher's presence has received permission and his status as a researcher is known by the source or informant.

Research Stages

1. The first stage

Researchers conducted interviews with research subjects to obtain information in this research.

2. Second Stage

- a. Observing teachers' teaching methods and learning atmosphere at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang.
- b. Obtain information about the teaching methods used by teachers and the learning atmosphere at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang.
- c. Researchers conducted research on whether teaching methods and learning atmosphere were adequate and their influence on students' level of understanding.
- d. The results of this research will be used as consideration by teachers to maintain or improve teaching methods and learning atmosphere at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang.

Data source

1. Primary Data: The data taken by researchers were observations and interviews from a teacher who taught at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang.
2. Secondary Data, Data obtained by researchers from internet literature.

Data Collection Procedures

1. Observation (observation)
2. Interview
3. Documentation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this research, researchers analyzed the teachers' teaching methods and the learning atmosphere at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang and evaluated whether the teaching methods and learning atmosphere were effective in increasing students' understanding of learning. The following are the teachers' teaching methods and the learning atmosphere that will be provided. explained according to research accompanied by discussion.

Teaching Methods

The teaching method used by the teacher is an important factor that can influence whether or not students understand the learning provided. The teachers at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang themselves use several methods as follows.

1. Lecture method

This method is a method that is often used by teachers, including teachers at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang. This method is usually used to explain material that is difficult for students to understand, so teachers at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang usually tell students to stop, take notes and focus on listening to the teachers in front.

2. Discussion Method

This method is usually used by teachers when they have finished explaining the material. Students are invited to discuss with their classmates or form groups and discuss the material that has been discussed.

3. Question and answer method

The question and answer method is carried out after the students have finished discussing with their classmates or groups. Usually teachers will ask their students to ask questions about material topics that are difficult to understand.

4. Portfolio Method

This method is used after students really understand the material. Usually teachers will give assignments that can hone their thinking skills and sensitivity to the surrounding environment. Such as counting, drawing, coloring, making works from used goods, or inviting them to throw rubbish in their place. .

Learning Atmosphere

The learning atmosphere is also no less important for a teacher and students because it is a very important supporting factor. Without a supportive learning atmosphere, students will not absorb the material optimally so their level of understanding will be less.

MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang is a school located in a rural area, so the atmosphere there is still beautiful and calm. This atmosphere is what is needed in the teaching and learning process because there is nothing to disturb the focus when the teaching and learning process begins.

Apart from adequate facilities, the teachers there also try to create a supportive learning environment by having students interact with their friends so that no student will feel excluded.

Providing learning motivation is also no less important for maintaining students' psychology and creating a learning atmosphere that supports learning activities. By providing motivation, students will have goals and be motivated to learn so that their future goals will be achieved. However, there are also various challenges in learning motivation. This is when the teacher's role is needed because it can provide inspiration as well as play a supporting role in overcoming obstacles to students' learning motivation.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The teaching methods applied by teachers at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang are quite successful in increasing students' level of understanding of learning. These methods are in the form of lectures, discussions, question and answer and portfolio methods.
2. The learning atmosphere at MI Miftahul Ulum Karangkonang is quite supportive in learning activities. Coupled with adequate facilities, this will be able to increase students' level of understanding of the material.
3. Providing learning motivation is also an important thing that can stimulate students' enthusiasm for learning and achieving goals.

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